

Playing the Virtual Glass Armonica

Astrid Pedersen, Morten Jørgensen, Halfdan Isaksen, Mikkel Riedel

Aalborg University Copenhagen

aekp19, mojarg19, hisaks19, mriedel19@student.aau.dk

ABSTRACT

The continuation of research and technological advances within the field of virtual reality (VR) and haptics, further facilitates new interaction opportunities, which can be created for virtual reality musical instruments (VRMIs). Integrated in a museum setting, this can allow for new ways for both users and scholars to interact with, and learn about, musical artifacts, which otherwise would be contained behind glass cases. In this paper, the authors design and implement a virtual Glass Armonica, synthesized with the FAUST Physical Modeling ToolKit, to be played with the wearable haptic interface, WeArt TouchDiver; providing force-, temperature- and vibrotactile feedback to enhance playability. This is done with the purpose of providing an immersive cultural experience in a historically accurate virtual environment (VE), for the visitors at the Danish Music Museum in Copenhagen.

1. INTRODUCTION

The interactive and multimodal experiences enabled by VR platforms, continues to gain prominence as a medium for artistic expression. Development in the field of musical interaction design has enabled researchers to explore novel affordances of creatively expressive musical interfaces. Furthermore, as the rapid development and availability of interactive technologies reaches public establishments, VR experiences are increasingly being included in museum institutions to further assist the cultural experience [1].

In collaboration with the Danish Music Museum, this paper aims to present the theoretical reasoning, and implementation of an interactive musical interface, replicating the Glass Armonica in an immersive VE, communicating the rich history of the instrument. Playing the Glass Armonica much resembles that of rubbing the edge of a wine-glass with a moist finger. The instrument, invented by Benjamin Franklin, adopts glass bowls turned by a horizontal axle. This way, the side of the bowls are submerged into a trough of water [2]. As playing the instrument produces multiple tactile cues, the haptic device of choice was the WeArt TouchDiver, which provides haptic actuators much aligning with the haptic sensations of playing the original counterpart.

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2. RELATED WORKS

Musical interfaces in VR has been implemented in museums in order to both promote and increase accessibility of historical instruments, in ways not normally accessible to the visitor. In [3], two mixed reality applications were developed to promote the *Guqin*, a traditional Chinese string instrument. A field study revealed an overwhelming increase in interest of the instrument after using their VR system. Likewise in [4], traditional instruments were simulated and recreated in a culturally communicative VE to enhance the users' sense of on-site experience; which increased the depth of cultural communication. VR experiences thereby not only has the potential to display the instrument multimodally, but also its historical context, communicated through the immersive VE.

The expressive musical interfaces have been coined as VRMIs [5]. Following the definition, Serafin et al. establishes a set of nine conceptual design principles; first of which discusses the design for feedback and mapping. When playing an acoustic instrument, an intense haptic experience is not only unavoidable, but also highly relevant to the playability [5]. The correlation between auditory and haptic modalities has been a widespread topic of research, and has received increasing interest in the field of sound and music computing [6]. In [7], Avanzini et al. suggests a multimodal architecture, integrating physically-based sound models with haptic and visual rendering. Their experimental results revealed evidence of how auditory feedback can modulate tactile perception of contact stiffness. In the works of [8], Papetti et al. emphasizes the role of haptics in the complex action-perception loop for instrument performance, and furthermore highlights the absence between sound production and active haptic feedback for current digital musical instruments.

In the context of cultural heritage, providing haptic feedback would potentially not only increase the playability of the musical interface, but also enable the visitor to touch the past, possibly offering an immersive cultural experience [5, 9].

3. HAPTIC INTERFACE

For reproducing haptic feedback aligning with that of playing the Glass Armonica in real life, the haptic device WeArt TouchDiver was employed. The vibrotactile actuators provides a bandwidth for texture rendering (20-500Hz), thermal feedback enabling material discrimination with 0.1°C resolution, and up to 7N for skin indentation with resolution of 0,05N; on the tips of the thumb, index, and mid-

Figure 1. First iteration 3D model of the Glass Armonica

dle fingers. The user plays the Glass Armonica with continuous contact, as the finger must apply the appropriate amount of continuous force, before actuating vibrations and producing sound. When replicating the musical interface, the mapping between the haptic output is therefore relevant for the playability, as the force-actuated vibrations will guide the user to produce the auditory feedback. Additionally, as the instrument require application of water before being able to produce sound, this introduces the potential of including thermal feedback. How this contributes to the playability is uncertain, but if a realistic rendering of the interaction is desired, it would be conceivable to include.

4. SOUND SYNTHESIS AND IMPLEMENTATION

The sounds of the Glass Armonica were simulated using FAUST Physical Modeling ToolKit. The toolkit provides a set of virtual musical instruments based on physical modelling. The notes assigned to the playable bowls were approximated from listening to Glass Armonica samples. An overarching benefit of physical modelling, is that the physical parameters of the model can be controlled by user actions [7]. In the perspective of the Glass Armonica, the physical parameter of Bow Pressure was mapped to the force index of the haptic device, controlled by the location of the virtual hand. Ultimately letting the user control the amplitude of the sound produced, based on pressure applied onto the virtual glass bowl.

The 3D instrument, seen on figure 1, and other models in the VE, were modelled using Blender before being implemented in Unity 3D. The WeArt TouchDiver offers an SDK compatible with Unity, facilitating easy control and mapping of the actuators featured in the device. For hand-tracking, the haptic device was mounted on an HTC Vive Tracker, and visuals were rendered through an HTC Vive Pro head-mounted display.

5. CONCLUSIONS

As the technological development of interactive experiences increases accessibility, VR is more commonly being implemented in public establishment; such as museums. Based on existing design frameworks of VRMIs, the design of feedback for the Glass Armonica using active haptics, is now increasingly conceivable with the WeArt TouchDiver.

Implementing an interactive musical interface will, in the context of cultural heritage, not only provide access for

visitors to experience the acoustics of the instrument, but also the historical context; giving way for not only musical expressivity in VR, but also a platform for cultural dissemination.

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6. REFERENCES

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